

Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) Proficiency Levels of Key Stage 1 Learners: Instructional Supervision -Based Study

Metchie P. Purisima

Graduate Student, Colegio de Santa Rita de San Carlos, Inc.

Melissa S. Ygay, MAEd

Graduate School Instructor, Colegio de Santa Rita de San Carlos, Inc

Abstract: This study examined Comprehensive Rapid Literacy (CRLA) Proficiency Levels of Key Stage 1 Learners: Instructional Supervision-Base Study. The study evaluated the effect of structured instructional supervision on primary students' early literacy development using a one-group pretest-posttest methodology. 39 elementary school teachers and their Grades 1-3 students participated in the study. They were assessed using standardized reading assessment instruments that measured vocabulary, comprehension, fluency, and phonics and were in line with CRLA (Comprehensive Rapid and Literacy Assessment) criteria. The five main goals of the instructional supervision program were to: strengthen classroom reading environments and provide access to relevant materials; monitor student progress using evidence-based assessments; improve CRLA-aligned reading proficiency through structured supervision; build teachers' capacity through targeted coaching and feedback; and cultivate a positive learning culture that supports literacy development. Workshops on CRLA reading standards, efficient assessment procedures, data-driven lesson planning, and coaching with useful criticism were all part of the teacher preparation program. The findings showed that reading proficiency had significantly increased at every grade level. The majority of students were categorized as Light Refresher and Moderate Refresher levels prior to intervention. Students categorized as Grade Ready increased significantly after the intervention, while those in the Moderate and Full Refresher categories significantly decreased. In Grades 1-3, statistically significant differences between pretest and posttest scores were confirmed by a paired sample t-test at the 0.05 level of significance. Additionally, teachers expressed favorable opinions of the supervision program, demonstrating greater self-assurance and readiness to teach reading. The "CLRA Reading Supervisory Program: Enhancing Literacy Skills" was created as a result of the study's findings.

Key words: Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA), Reading Proficiency, Instructional Supervision, Key Stage 1 Learners, District 1, Cluster 2, San Carlos City.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Early literacy has increasingly become a priority in education, as strong reading skills in the early grades are closely linked to later academic success and lifelong learning. While the global organizations such as UNESCO and the World Bank underscore the importance of early reading proficiency (UNESCO, 2021, 2022; Word Bank, 2021), the disruption caused by the COVID-19 pandemic magnified existing learning gaps, especially among young learners. In the Philippines, similar challenges have been observed, where limited access to technology, inconsistent remote learning conditions, and the absence of face-to-face instruction have hindered reading development in the early grades. (Aquino & Bautista, 2022). These broader trends have shaped how local schools respond to reading challenges, but the realities on the ground particularly in rural and semi-urban divisions like San Carlos City, require more context-specific approach.

Within San Carlos City schools in District 1, Cluster 2 have undertaken various reading interventions such as Project READS, remedial reading sessions, and parent-led home reading programs to address post-pandemic deficits among Grade 1-3 pupils. However, the effectiveness of these programs often depends on the quality of instructional supervision provided to teachers. Recent local assessments indicate the need for stronger supervisory practices, including more frequent classroom observations, constructive feedback, targeted coaching, and structured monitoring tools (Reyes, 2024). Despite these efforts, local schools face persistent issues such as limited supervisory time, insufficient professional development resources, and inconsistent follow through, all of which affects the consistency and quality of reading instruction. These challenges highlight that while reading program exist, their outcomes may vary considerably depending on how will instructional supervision supports teachers at the classroom level.

Recent observations and local reports in San Carlos City suggest a growing need for enhanced supervisory practices to better support teachers in implementing effective reading strategies. While formal peer-reviewed studies in this area remain limited, preliminary findings and school-level assessments indicate that teachers who receive regular, constructive feedback through practices such as classroom observations, coaching sessions, and the use of structured observation tools are more likely to apply evidence-based reading instruction and achieve improved student outcomes. Enhanced supervisory practices may involve more frequent and purposeful classroom visits, the use of standardized observation rubrics, targeted mentoring for struggling teachers, and follow-up conferences focused on actionable feedback. However, existing challenges such as limited time for supervisory visits, insufficient resources for ongoing professional development, and the need for differentiated support continue to hinder the full effectiveness of these practices. These gaps underscore the importance of investigating how instructional supervision can be strengthened to better support reading proficiency, particularly in early grade levels.

The implementation of instructional supervision programs in San Carlos City Schools has been influenced by various factors, including the level of support from school administrators, and the commitment of teachers to improving their instructional practices. Understanding the impact of these factors on the effectiveness of instructional supervision is crucial for informing policy and practice at the local level.

The gap that emerges from the existing literature and local reports is the lack of empirical evidence on how instructional supervision specifically influences early grade reading proficiency in San Carlos City, particularly within District 1, Cluster 2. Most studies either discuss supervision in general terms or focus on global and national trends, with few providing concrete data on learning outcomes tied to local supervisory practices. To address this, the present study examines the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) Proficiency levels of Key Stage 1 learners: Instructional Supervision-Based Study in District 1. By comparing pre and post test results, the study seeks to determine the extent to which strengthened supervision contributes to improved reading outcomes in the specific locality. The findings will offer actionable insights for local educators, school leaders, and policymakers aiming to refine supervisory strategies and enhance early literacy instruction in San Carlos City.

Review of Related Literature

This chapter presented a review of both local and foreign literature and studies relevant to reading proficiency among early grade learners, factors affecting literacy development, and the influence of instructional supervision programs on teaching effectiveness and student achievement.

Instructional Supervision

Instructional supervision refers to the continuous process of supporting and guiding teachers to improve their instructional practices. Recent empirical studies in Asian contexts have emphasized that instructional supervision is not only about evaluation but also involves mentoring, coaching, and

providing metacognitive support to teachers, which significantly enhances their pedagogical competence. Moreover, instructional supervision has been linked to higher teacher efficacy and job satisfaction, suggesting that when supervisors engage in sustained, supportive practices, teachers feel more confident and committed in their roles. Empirical studies suggest a strong link between instructional supervision and pupils' reading proficiency. When teachers receive targeted supervision focusing on reading instruction, they are more likely to implement effective strategies that improve literacy skills (Calderon, 2021). In Garcia's (2021) study, pupils in supervised classes showed higher gains in reading comprehension and vocabulary.

In another study, Santos (2022) reported that instructional leadership practices that emphasized mentoring and classroom observation led to significant improvements in learners' reading scores. These findings underscore that supervision is not merely evaluative but developmental, aiming to uplift both teacher capability and learner performance. A study found a significant positive correlation between instructional supervision and teacher efficacy, indicating that supervision helps empower teachers and improve classroom practices. (Quilala & Tantiado, 2025)

(Febrina et al., 2024), They reported that instructional supervision significantly influences teacher pedagogical competence and, indirectly, student achievement in Indonesian elementary schools. A study discussed the challenges in school supervision, noting that consistent coaching, feedback, and resource support are essential for improving teacher professionalism and instructional quality. (Desrianti & Asmendri, 2023)

In the Philippines, a recent study showed that intentional mentoring strategies (SHIMS) led by school heads through reflective supervision have a positive impact on beginning teachers' instructional delivery and self-reflection. According to RSIS International, these findings were documented by Norman R. Galabo, EdD, who emphasized the role of structured mentoring in strengthening classroom practices. The study also highlighted that SHIMS promotes continuous professional dialogue, allowing novice teachers to better understand their instructional strengths and areas for growth. Moreover, regular reflective sessions foster greater teacher confidence and commitment to improving learner outcomes.

Victorynie & Othman (2023) explored academic supervision practices in Indonesian Islamic schools and found that such supervision helps teachers solve instructional problems and improve performance through a supervisor-support program. According to Sultan et al. (2025), they demonstrated that academic supervision (a form of instructional supervision) by school principals in Indonesia positively correlates with teacher performance, especially when combined with strong leadership and teacher motivation.

Metille & Patiño (2025) studied instructional supervision in a district in the Philippines and argued that ongoing, structured supervision is a vehicle for teacher professional development, especially under newer policy frameworks (e.g., DepEd Order No. 24, s. 2020).

In the Philippine education system, instructional supervision is an important responsibility of school heads and master teachers, helping ensure that teaching practices continue to improve. According to Garcia (2021), both students' academic achievement and teachers' classroom performance significantly improved in schools with structured and regular supervising programs. Similarly, Santos (2022) demonstrated how teachers might deliver reading lessons more successfully and improve students' reading competency by frequent monitoring, mentoring, and insightful feedback. Together, these studies highlight that instructional supervision does more than guide teachers it supports their professional growth and helps create learning experiences that truly benefit students. This makes it important to look closely at how instructional supervision is carried out in specific schools and how it affects both teaching quality and student learning.

Reading Proficiency

Reading is an essential skill that forms the foundation of all learning. It is the key to success in all academic areas, as it enables learners to comprehend, analyze, and apply information. According to the National Reading Panel (2020), reading proficiency includes the ability to decode words accurately, read fluently, and comprehend text meaningfully. For learners in Grades 1–3, the development of reading skills is crucial, as these are the formative years when children transition from learning to read toward reading to learn.

Recent research also shows that reading proficiency is strongly influenced by both individual-level and school-level factors: for example, a multilevel study in Southeast Asia found that socioeconomic status, school climate, and student well-being significantly predict reading performance.

Moreover, affective and cognitive factors such as motivation, grit, and anxiety have been linked to comprehension: in an Asian context, task-based instruction was found to enhance reading comprehension by reducing anxiety and increasing motivation and grit in L2 readers. Sayed M. Ismail et al.

According to Darmawan & Dharmapatni (2024), multilevel analysis of student- and school-level factors (e.g., socioeconomic status, social well-being, behavioral climate) that are associated with reading performance among 15-year-olds in several Southeast Asian countries. In the Asian-Pacific context, they studied the impact of task-based instruction on reading comprehension and found that such instruction improves L2 reading comprehension by influencing learners' motivation, grit, and anxiety. (Ismail, et al., 2023).

In the recent study of Rachel C. Macawile & Jocelyn S. Castro (2025). They examined how teacher, student, home, and environmental factors influence reading proficiency (measured via the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory). They found that teacher-related and environmental factors had significant associations with reading ability. They explored what factors are associated with Grade 3 pupils' reading performance in the Philippines, showing that lack of parental support, reading materials at home, and negative attitudes or poor study habits correlate with low reading performance. (Cherrylene Costino-Sanoria & Richard M. Oco, 2023).

According to Barrios and Tabanera (2023), pupils' comprehension skills in the early grades are still developing, and many require structured intervention and teacher support. They emphasize that without guided practice and explicit instruction, young learners often struggle to make meaning from text, especially when vocabulary and background knowledge are limited. The authors also note that early, consistent exposure to reading activities both at home and in school significantly strengthens children's comprehension growth. Therefore, targeted intervention programs and sustained classroom support are essential to ensure that learners progress from basic decoding toward deeper understanding of texts.

Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment play a vital role in improving pupil's reading proficiency particularly in the early grades where foundation literacy skills are still developing. Recent studies highlight that structured, teacher -guided reading activities significantly influence learners' comprehension and decoding abilities. Macawile and Castro(2025) found that teacher-related factors, including instructional strategies and classroom practices, as well as environmental factors, have a significant relationship with pupil's reading proficiency as measured by the Comprehensive reading and literacy assessment(CRLA). This suggests that consistent and well-designed classroom reading activities are crucial in supporting learners' reading development.

Similarly, Constantino-Sanoria and Oco (2023) reported that pupil's low reading performance is associated with limited parental support, insufficient reading materials at home, and poor study habits. These findings underscore the importance of Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) as a compensatory mechanism within the classroom., especially for learners who lack adequate literacy support at home. Through guided reading, repeated exposure to texts, and interactive reading tasks,can

help Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) bridge gaps in learners' reading experiences and promote better comprehension outcomes.

Barios and Tabanera(2023) further emphasizes that pupil's comprehension skills in the early grades required explicit instruction, guided practice, and sustained teacher support. Without structured classroom reading activities, many learners' struggle to construct meaning from texts due to limited vocabulary and background knowledge. Regular implementation of Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA), both in school and reinforced through home-based reading tasks, strengthen learners' comprehension growth and supports their transition from basic decoding to higher-level understanding.

In the Philippine context, the Department of Education has institutionalized reading initiatives such as the Every Child Reader Program (ECARP) and the use of Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA). Despite these efforts, national and local assessment indicated that many pupils remain below expected reading proficiency levels (Navarra, 2023). This continuing gap highlights the need to strengthen Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) implementation and examine its effectiveness in improving reading proficiency across different learning contexts. Hence, further research on the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) and its impact on pupils' reading performance is essential to enhance existing reading programs and ensure that all learners achieve functional literacy.

Synthesis

Instructional supervision has evolved into a key mechanism for enhancing teaching quality and supporting learner achievement across global and Asian contexts. Scholars consistently emphasize that supervision is no longer confined to evaluative functions but is increasingly viewed as a developmental process that strengthens teacher growth, professional competence, and instructional effectiveness. As schools, including those within District 1, Cluster 2 of San Carlos City, face pressures to improve literacy and academic performance, effective supervision supported by strong school management and sustained teacher motivation has become essential to maintaining high-quality teaching and learning. Literature consistently shows that supervision grounded in mentoring, coaching, and reflective dialogue significantly elevates teacher performance and contributes to stronger student learning outcomes, particularly in foundational areas such as reading.

Across the reviewed studies, instructional supervision is portrayed as a multifaceted and dynamic process that supports teachers' professional development. Research highlights that contemporary supervision integrates mentoring, coaching, and metacognitive guidance rather than focusing solely on evaluating teacher performance. These expanded supervisory roles enable teachers to refine their pedagogical skills, enhance their instructional decision-making, and develop greater confidence and job satisfaction. Supportive and collaborative supervision has been shown to empower teachers in improving their classroom practices. Moreover, effective supervision directly strengthens teachers' pedagogical competence and indirectly promotes student achievement, affirming its broader influence on overall learning outcomes an insight that is highly relevant to schools in District 1, Cluster 2 of San Carlos City.

The literature also underscores the interconnected relationship between instructional supervision and school management practices. Successful supervision depends not only on the technical expertise of school supervisors but also on the presence of consistent coaching, constructive feedback, and adequate school resources. In the Philippine context, studies highlight that structured and reflective supervisory frameworks enhance the instructional delivery and professional growth of beginning and experienced teachers alike. Sustained, policy-aligned supervision provides a strong foundation for teacher development, emphasizing the crucial role of effective school leadership. For schools in District 1, Cluster 2 of San Carlos City, such leadership-driven supervision is vital in building a supportive and growth-oriented instructional environment.

Furthermore, instructional supervision plays a significant role in shaping teacher motivation and performance, which ultimately influences student learning. Research demonstrates that supervisory programs that provide guidance, encouragement, and problem-solving support help teachers overcome instructional challenges, thereby strengthening their motivation and work performance. The effectiveness of supervision is amplified when combined with leadership approaches that cultivate teacher enthusiasm and engagement. This interdependent relationship among instructional supervision, school management support, and teacher motivation mirrors the lived realities of teachers in District 1, Cluster 2 of San Carlos City, where supportive leadership is essential for sustaining teacher commitment and instructional excellence.

Finally, a substantial body of literature highlights a direct connection between instructional supervision and students' reading proficiency. Studies show that when teachers receive targeted supervision focused on reading instruction, learners demonstrate improvements in comprehension, vocabulary, and overall literacy achievement. These findings affirm that high-quality supervision contributes not only to teacher competence but also to better student performance in foundational literacy. Overall, the reviewed literature emphasizes that instructional supervision anchored in mentoring, reflective dialogue, and strategic leadership is indispensable for elevating teaching quality, strengthening teacher motivation, and improving student outcomes. For schools in District 1, Cluster 2 of San Carlos City, enhancing supervisory practices remains a critical step toward building a high-performing and learner-centered educational system.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on three interrelated theories: Jean Piaget's Cognitive Development Theory, Lev Vygotsky's Social Constructivism, and the Theory of Instructional Supervision developed by Glickman, Gordon, and Ross Gordon (2010). These theories provide a foundational understanding of how children learn, how instruction affects learning outcomes, and how supervision can enhance teaching quality and, in turn, student performance.

The way students in Grades 1-3 learn and comprehend what they read is explained by Jean Piaget's theory of cognitive development. According to Piaget (1952), children at this age are in the concrete operational stage, where they start to reason more logically and gain a greater understanding of language, concepts, and pattern skills crucial for developing into effective readers. Additionally, he stressed that children learn best when they actively participate in activities that are appropriate for their cognitive level. This means that when it comes to teaching reading, classes should be tailored to the ways in which young students acquire information and should promote meaningful interaction with books. According to Piaget's theory, an instructional monitoring program can help teachers employ developmentally appropriate practices that can help students become more proficient readers.

Lev Vygotsky's social constructivist theory supports this study by emphasizing how important guided learning is for young children who are developing their reading skills. His concept of the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) characterizes the gap between what students can perform independently and what they can achieve with the assistance of a more experienced mentor (Vygotsky, 1978). This zone includes several reading skills for students in Grades 1-3, including word decoding, developing fluency, and comprehending texts. As a result, students frequently require structured guidance from their teachers. In this sense, instructional supervision becomes a valuable tool because it helps teachers improve their methods through mentoring, feedback, and modeling. Teachers are better able to give their students the appropriate amount of assistance when they receive this kind of support. Thus, Vygotsky's theory emphasizes how good instructional supervision can improve reading instruction and assist young students in making significant progress.

Glickman, Gordon, and Ross-Gordon's (2010) Theory of Instructional Supervision serves as an important foundation for this study by viewing supervision as a supportive and developmental process

that helps teachers grow and, in turn, improves student learning. The approach emphasizes useful supervisory techniques that help teachers improve their instruction, including coaching, feedback, classroom observations, and professional development.

It further clarifies that based on the needs and experience level of the teacher, supervisors can employ a variety of strategies, including directive, collaborative, and non-directive. According to the theory, monitoring should assist in ensuring that instructional strategies for early-grade reading are in line with efficient, empirically supported approaches to literacy development. The clinical supervision cycle, in which supervisors watch lessons, offer feedback, and assist teachers in reflecting on their work so they can make quick improvements, is a crucial component of this paradigm. Overall, this theory supports the notion that meaningful supervision fosters teacher development and improves young learners' reading outcomes.

The three theories, Vygotsky's social constructivism, Piaget's cognitive development, and Glickman et al.'s Theory of Instructional Supervision, are all intimately related to this research because they clarify how young students acquire reading skills and how teachers might assist them. According to Piaget, reading instruction is most effective when it is tailored to the cognitive capacities of students in Grades 1-3. According to Vygotsky, when teachers offer direction and support within their Zone of Proximal Development, children learn more efficiently.

According to Glickman et al., instructional monitoring aids educators in refining their approaches, evaluating their work, and implementing successful teaching techniques. Together, these theories support to the notion that integrating structured supervision, guided support, and developmentally appropriate instruction can improve student reading outcomes and teacher effectiveness.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

This conceptual framework illustrates how instructional supervision influences the reading proficiency of Grades 1–3 pupils, using survey data from principals, teachers, and learners to develop a reading supervisory program aimed at improving early-grade reading outcomes in District 1, Cluster 2.

Moreover, the framework is anchored in the idea that effective instructional supervision enhances teacher competence, which in turn positively shapes learners' reading development. By examining variables such as supervisory practices, teacher instructional behaviors, and pupils' reading performance, the framework highlights the interconnected roles of school leaders, teachers, and learners in the literacy process. It recognizes that early-grade reading proficiency is influenced not only by classroom instruction but also by the quality of guidance and feedback teachers receive from supervisors. Thus, the conceptual framework provides a systematic approach for identifying gaps in supervision, informing interventions, and ultimately designing a reading supervisory program that directly responds to the needs of early-grade learners in District 1, Cluster 2.

Statement of the Problem

This study sought to identify the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) reading proficiency levels of Key stage 1 learners before and after an instructional supervision program.

Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following question:

1. What is the level of Instructional Supervision of Key Stage 1 teachers before the Implementation of instructional supervision of their reading proficiency in terms of:
 - a. feedback and coaching for reading instruction;
 - b. classroom environment, materials, and assessment for reading and
 - c. teacher support and professional learning?
2. What is the level of the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) reading proficiency of the key stage 1 learners in terms of:
 - a. before the implementation of the instructional supervision and
 - b. after the implementation of the instructional supervision?
3. Is there a significant difference in key stage 1 learners before and after the instructional supervision intervention in their reading proficiency?
4. Based on the findings, what specific Key Stage 1 Reading Supervision Program can be recommended to improve learners' Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) reading proficiency in District 1, Cluster 2, San Carlos City?

Hypothesis

HA: There is a significant difference in the reading proficiency of Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) scores of key stage 1 learners before and after the instructional supervision intervention.

Significance of the Study

This study is significant as it determines the direct impact of instructional supervision on the reading proficiency levels of key stage 1 Learners in District 1, Cluster 2 of San Carlos City.

School Administrators. This serves as a basis for strengthening supervision frameworks and policies by identifying effective supervisory strategies so that school heads and coordinators can better support teachers in improving instructional delivery, particularly in early literacy.

Students. This study is significant to the students in helping them identify their specific reading strengths and weaknesses before and after the instructional supervision program, allowing them to receive more targeted support that can improve their reading skills, boost their confidence, and enhance their overall academic performance.

Teachers. The study highlights the value of continuous professional guidance and feedback through supervision in understanding the relationship between supervisory practices and student reading outcomes, which may encourage more reflective teaching and openness to pedagogical improvement.

Curriculum Planners and Policy Makers. The results may inform the design of reading programs, teacher development modules, and supervision protocols that align with national literacy goals and it offers empirical evidence on whether structured supervision translates into measurable academic gains.

Future Researchers. This study contributes to the growing literature on instructional supervision and its effects on learning outcomes. It can serve as a reference for conducting similar studies in other contexts or exploring additional variables that affect reading proficiency.

Scope of the Study

This study examines the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) reading proficiency levels of Key Stage 1 learners in District 1, Cluster 2 of San Carlos City during School Year 2025–2026. It investigates how the implementation of an Instructional Supervision Program for teachers influences pupils' reading performance in areas such as phonemic awareness, vocabulary, comprehension, and fluency.

The study involves all participating Key stage 1 learners from selected schools within the district and uses a quantitative/descriptive-comparative design to determine the impact of instructional supervision on reading proficiency.

The study is limited to the reading domains covered by the program and does not compare pupils to those from other districts or clusters. External factors such as home reading environment or socioeconomic status are also not considered.

Definition of Terms

For a clear understanding and to avoid confusion of the terms used in the study, the following terms are defined operationally.

Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA). Operationally, it refers to the scores obtained by pupils in the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment administered by the teacher. The test includes reading passages and questions that measures pupils' comprehension, vocabulary, and reading ability. The pupils' performance is based on their total scores in the CRLA.

Pre-test–Posttest Design. Operationally, it refers to the administration of the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) reading assessment to the same group of key stage 1 learners before the implementation of the instructional supervision program (pretest) and after the program has been carried out (posttest).

Reading Domains. Operationally, it refers to the specific skill areas measured through the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) assessment such as word recognition, oral reading fluency, and reading comprehension which are used to determine the Key Stage 1 learner's reading proficiency levels before and after the instructional supervision program.

Reading Proficiency Level. Operationally, it refers to the specific categories assigned to key stage 1 learners based on their Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) results (Full Refresher, Moderate Refresher, Light Refresher, and Grade Ready).

Reading Supervision Program. Operationally, it refers to the set of structured supervisory activities implemented by the school, such as scheduled classroom observations, feedback sessions, teacher coaching, and monitoring of reading instruction in District 1, Cluster 2.

CHAPTER 2

METHODOLOGY

This chapter introduces the methodological aspects of the study, encompassing the research design, respondents of the study, research instrument, data collection procedures, data analysis techniques, statistical treatment, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

This study uses a quantitative/descriptive-design, Comparative design is a pre-experimental research design in which a single group of participants is measured before and after an intervention to determine whether the treatment produces a change in the outcome variable. This design measures changes in the reading proficiency of key stage 1 learners before and after the implementation of an instructional supervision intervention. This method is appropriate since it allows the researcher to determine whether there is a significant difference in reading proficiency levels before and after the implementation of instructional supervision, even without a control group.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study are the key stage 1 learners enrolled in selected public elementary schools in District 1, Cluster 2, San Carlos City. These pupils are the focus of the research, as the study aims to determine their reading proficiency levels before and after the implementation of the Instructional Supervision Program.

The selection of respondents will be based on the schools included in the supervision program. All learners from the identified grade levels will undergo both pretest and posttest reading assessments using the same standardized or teacher-made reading tools to measure changes in their reading proficiency levels. In addition, the teachers handling Grades 1–3 and the school head or instructional supervisors may also be involved as secondary respondents to provide insights into the implementation and monitoring of the instructional supervision program. However, the primary data on reading proficiency will be derived from the pupils' test results.

Table 1. *Respondents of the Study*

School (Grades 1, 2 and 3 Teachers)	Population
Ansulag Elementary School	3
Camaniagan Elementary School	3
Greenville Elementary School	13
Katiclan Elementary School	3
Medina Integrated School	5
Nabataan Elementary School	3
Rizal Elementary School	3
School of the Future	6
Total	39

Research Instrument

The primary research instrument used in this study was a standardized Reading Proficiency Assessment designed for early-grade learners. Adapted from the Department of Education's validated reading tools and aligned with the key components of early literacy decoding, fluency, vocabulary, and comprehension the instrument measured learners reading levels across Grades 1 to 3. The assessment consisted of grade-

appropriate oral reading passages, word-recognition tasks, and comprehension questions that allowed for the accurate identification of learners' independent, instructional, and frustration reading levels. Its structure ensured that reading competencies were evaluated systematically, producing consistent and reliable measurements both before and after the implementation of the instructional supervision program.

To supplement the pupil assessment, structured survey questionnaires were administered to school principals and teachers to gather data on the instructional supervision practices implemented during the program. These questionnaires were researcher-made and content-validated by experts in reading education and school leadership, ensuring that the items accurately captured supervisory activities such as classroom observation, coaching, feedback provision, and mentoring. Together, the Reading Proficiency Assessment and the supervisory practice surveys provided comprehensive data on how instructional supervision influenced classroom instruction and, consequently, the reading proficiency outcomes of key stage 1 learners in District 1, Cluster 2.

Validity and Reliability of Survey Questionnaires.

The results of the content validation indicate that the research instrument is highly valid, as evidenced by an overall mean rating of 4.94, interpreted as excellent. All criteria were consistently rated very high by the jurors, suggesting that the questionnaire clearly, accurately, and effectively measures the variables of the study. This confirms that the instrument is appropriate for assessing the reading proficiency levels of Grades 1,2 and 3 pupils before and after the instructional supervision program in District 1, Cluster 2, San Carlos City. Thus, the instrument is deemed suitable for data gathering and can generate reliable and meaningful results for the study.

The reliability of the research instrument was determined using Cronbach's Alpha, a statistical measure used to assess the internal consistency of questionnaire items measured through a five-point Likert scale. The analysis yielded a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.931 for the 15-item instrument, which indicates excellent reliability. This high coefficient signifies that the items in the questionnaire are highly consistent and effectively measure the same construct.

The result implies that the instrument produces stable and dependable responses, minimizing measurement errors and ensuring consistency across respondents. Thus, the questionnaire with utilized a Likert scale, is considered reliable for assessing the reading proficiency levels of Grades 1,2 and 3 pupils before and after the instructional supervision program in District 1, Cluster 2, San Carlos City. The application of Cronbach's Alpha as the statistical treatment further strengthens the credibility of the data gathered and supports the reliability of the study findings.

Data Collection Procedure

The researcher will secured written approval from the Schools Division Superintendent of San Carlos City, the District Supervisor of District 1, Cluster 2, and the heads of the participating schools. Parental consent forms will be distributed so that Grade 1–3 pupils participate voluntarily and ethically. All participating teachers will attend an orientation session to learn about the study objectives, their roles in administering the reading assessments, and the structure of the Instructional Supervision Program.

Following current DepEd guidelines, the pretest will be administered using a standardized reading assessment, the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) aligned with the frameworks outlined in recent memoranda (e.g., RM No. 145, s. 2023; RM No. 654, s. 2023). The assessment will include comprehension questions as well as oral and silent reading tasks, administered by trained teachers. Reading coordinators will verify scoring to ensure reliability; trained teachers will assign pupils to Independent, Instructional, or Frustration reading levels, and their assignments will be cross-checked by other scorers.

The Instructional Supervision Program will be implemented over 8–10 weeks, adopting a developmental supervision model blended with more recent coaching approaches documented in the literature. For example, the model draws on metacognitive supervision strategies and cognitive coaching-based supervision developed for literacy contexts. The activities will include classroom observations, coaching and mentoring sessions, demonstration of effective reading strategies, and structured reflection and feedback meetings. The researcher will monitor implementation with weekly check-ins and detailed documentation of supervisory interactions.

At the end of the supervision intervention, the same Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) tests will be administered again under the same conditions as the pretest. Scoring will be completed by trained teachers, and then independently reviewed by two separate scorers; any scoring discrepancies will be resolved through consensus. To analyze the data, the researcher will use a paired-sample t-test along with descriptive and inferential statistics in line with current social science methods. For statistical guidance, the researcher consults modern texts on instructional supervision and data analysis practices such as recent works on instructional supervision and organizational support.

Data Analysis Procedure

The pre-test and posttest scores from the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) will first be organized and entered into Microsoft Excel the imported into SPSS for analysis. In line with best practices, the data will be carefully examined for completeness, inconsistencies, scoring errors, and proper coding of categorical variables. Outliers and missing data will also be addressed before the main analysis. Before running inferential statistics, assumption checks (such as normality of difference scores) will be performed to ensure parametric test requirements are met.

Descriptive statistics will be used to illustrate the reading competency levels of key stage 1 learners before and after the instructional supervision program. Specifically, mean and standard deviation will reflect the central tendency and variability of pretest and posttest scores, while frequency and percentages will indicate how many pupils fall into each Phil-IRI reading level category (Independent, Instructional, Frustration)

To evaluate the effectiveness of the supervision intervention, a paired-sample t-test will be conducted to compare pupil's reading scores before and after the program. This is appropriate for the one-group pretest- posttest design. The statistical significance of any observed differences will be interpreted alongside effect size measures, when possible, to assess practical as well as statistical impact. Results will also be interpreted using the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) level description, allowing the researcher to contextualize gains in terms of reading level improvements.

Statistical Treatment

This study employed appropriate statistical treatments to analyze the pretest and posttest reading proficiency scores of key stage 1 learners, enabling the researcher to determine the effectiveness of the instructional supervision program implemented in District 1, Cluster 2.

Frequency Count and Percentage

These were used to determine the number and proportion of pupils under each reading proficiency category (Full Refresher, Moderate Refresher, Light Refresher, and Grade Ready) based on the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) pretest and posttest results.

Mean

The mean reading score was computed to determine the average performance of learners in both the pretest and posttest.

Standard Deviation

Used to determine the variability of learners' scores in both pretest and posttest.

Paired Sample t-test

A paired-sample t-test was used to determine whether there is a significant difference between learners' pretest and posttest reading scores.

Likert Scale

The Likert Scale can be used to measure the degree of reading proficiency of key stage 1 learners before and after the instructional supervision program based on teachers' or assessors' ratings of pupils' reading performance.

Table 2

Interpretation Level of the Instructional Supervision of Grades 1-3 Teachers

Scale	Weighted Means/Equivalent	Corresponding Remarks
5	4.21-5.00	Always
4	3.61-4.20	Often
3	2.41-3.60	Sometimes
2	2.81-2.40	Rarely
1	1.00-1.80	Never

Table 3

Interpretation Level of the Instructional Supervision of Grades 1-3 learners CRLA

Scale	Main Range	Interpretation
4	3.26- 4.00	Grade Ready (GR)
3	2.51-3.25	Light Refresher (LR)
2	1.76-2.50	Moderate Refresher (MR)
1	1.00-1.75	Full Refresher (FR)

Ethical Consideration

Adhering to the National Privacy Commission's guidelines, the researcher will inform data subjects (parents, students, teachers) about the data processing purpose, the categories of data collected, and their rights to access, correct, or object to the use of their information. Research participation will be voluntary, and participants may withdraw at any time without penalty.

The researcher also commits to ethical data retention: according to best practices, data will be kept only as long as necessary for the research's declared purposes and will be disposed of securely after use.

To minimize risk, only developmental (non-evaluative) feedback will be provided to teachers, meaning supervision outcomes will not affect teacher employment or performance evaluation. Reporting of results will be done in aggregate form, without attributing any data to individual students or teachers, thereby protecting their identities and ensuring anonymity.

Finally, the researcher will ensure the integrity of the research by reporting data honestly, avoiding fabrication or falsification, and transparently addressing any limitations. To further strengthen ethical standards, data handling and consent procedures will follow models like the UP Diliman Revised Privacy

Policy for Researchers and Research Subjects, which emphasizes minimizing data collected, strict confidentiality, and explicit informed consent.

To ensure the study's validity and comply with current Philippine data protection regulations, the researcher will secure written authorization from the San Carlos City Schools Division Superintendent, the District Supervisor for District 1, Cluster 2, and the principals of all participating elementary schools. Informed consent forms will be provided to parents or legal guardians of key stage 1 learners, clearly explaining the study's goals, procedures, potential risks and benefits, measures for confidentiality, and the voluntary nature of participation. Students will be included only if both their verbal assent and parental permission are obtained.

In line with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (RA 10173) and its Implementing Rules and Regulations (IRR), the study will uphold strict confidentiality and data protection standards. Personal data will be pseudonymized (coded identifiers), and no names or directly identifying information will appear in reports or publications. Data will be stored in encrypted or password-protected digital files to prevent unauthorized access.

CHAPTER 3

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter presents the results, analysis, and interpretation of data gathered from the questionnaires and documents in connection to the specific problems and hypothesis of this investigation.

The levels of instructional supervision of Grades 1,2,3 teachers before and after the implementation of instructional supervision of their proficiency in terms in their feedback and coaching for reading instruction, classroom environment, materials and assessment for reading and teacher support and professional learning.

Table 4A. *Levels of Instructional Supervision in Terms of Feedback and Coaching for Reading Instruction*

STATEMENTS	5		4		3		2		1		TOTAL	SD	WX	I
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%				
Prior to supervision, I had opportunities to discuss challenges in teaching reading with my supervisor and coach.	33	84.61	6	15.38	0	0	0	0	0	0	39	100	4.85	A
I was given actionable suggestions to enhance my reading instruction strategies.	32	82.1	7	17.94	0	0	0	0	0	0	39	100	4.82	A
Coaching sessions helped me identify areas for improving student's reading skills.	30	76.92	9	23.07	0	0	0	0	0	0	39	100	4.77	A
Feedback provided to me was timely and relevant to my reading lessons.	29	74.36	10	26.64	0	0	0	0	0	0	39	100	4.74	A
Before supervision, I received clear feedback on how to improve my reading instruction.	28	71.80	11	28.21	0	0	0	0	0	0	39	100	4.72	A
Total/General weighted mean	152	77.95	43	22.1	0	0	0	0	0	0	195	100	4.78	A

Legend:4.21-5.00 Always;3.61-4.20 Often;2.41-3.60 Sometimes; 2.81-2.40 Rarely; 1.00-1.80 Never

Table 4A presents the results for Feedback and Coaching for Reading Instruction. All items received very high ratings, with weighted mean scores ranging from 4.72 to 4.85 on a 5-point scale. The highest mean scores are 4.85 Prior to supervision, I had opportunities to discuss challenges in teaching reading with my supervision and coach and the lowest mean score was 4.72 before supervision. I received clear feedback on how to improve my reading instruction. Most respondents strongly agreed that supervisory feedback was clear, timely, and relevant, that coaching helped identify areas for improvement, and that

actionable suggestions were provided. The overall weighted mean of 4.78 indicates strong positive perceptions of the feedback and coaching process.

Table 4B. *Levels of Instructional Supervision in terms of Classroom Environment, Materials & Assessment for Reading*

STATEMENTS	5		4		3		2		1		TOTAL	SD	WX	I
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%				
B.														
I had access to adequate reading materials and resources before supervision.	31	73.81	11	26.19	0	0	0	0	0	0	42	100	4.96	A
My classroom setup was conducive to activities that support reading development.	32	76.19	10	23.81	0	0	0	0	0	0	42	100	4.76	A
My reading instructional materials supported diverse learners'	30	71.43	12	28.57	0	0	0	0	0	0	42	100	4.71	A
Students were provided with meaningful reading activities before supervision took place.	28	66.67	14	33.33	0	0	0	0	0	0	42	100	4.67	A
I used appropriate assessment tools to evaluate students' reading progress.	24	57.14	18	42.86	0	0	0	0	0	0	42	100	4.57	A
Total/General weighted mean	145	69.05	65	30.95	0	0	0	0	0	0	210		4.69	A
*											210			

Legend:4.21-5.00 Always;3.61-4.20 Often;2.41-3.60 Sometimes; 2.81-2.40 Rarely; 1.00-1.80 Never

Table 4B shows results for Classroom Environment, Materials, and Assessment for Reading. All items received high weighted means (4.57–4.69), indicating strong positive perceptions of the classroom setup and available reading resources. The highest mean was I had access to adequate reading materials and resources before supervision (4.96), The lowest mean (4.57) was when I used appropriate assessment tools to evaluate students’ reading progress. The overall weighted mean of 4.69 suggests that teachers generally view the classroom environment, materials, and assessments as supportive of reading instruction. These findings align with research showing that well-resourced classroom settings and effective assessment practices contribute to improved literacy outcomes (Rance et al., 2023)

Table 4C. *Levels of Instructional Supervision in terms of Teacher Support & Professional Learning*

STATEMENTS	5		4		3		2		1		TOTAL	SD	WX	I
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%				
C.														
I had access to professional learning opportunities related to teaching reading.	21	50	21	50	0	0	0	0	0	0	42	100	4.50	A
I was encouraged to develop professionally in the area of reading instruction.	21	50	21	50	0	0	0	0	0	0	42	100	4.50	A
Before supervision, I felt confident in addressing student' reading difficulties	20		22	52.38	0	0	0	0	0	0	42	100	4.48	A
		47.62												
Collaborative discussion with colleagues helped improve my reading instruction.	17		25	59.52	0	0	0	0	0	0	42	100	4.40	A
		40.48												
I received sufficient support in improving my reading instruction practices.	17	40.48	25	59.52	0	0	0	0	0	0	42	100	4.40	A
Total/General weighted mean	96	45.71	114	54.29	0	0	0	0	0	0	210	100	4.46	A
*														

Legend:4.21-5.00 Always;3.61-4.20 Often;2.41-3.60 Sometimes; 2.81-2.40 Rarely; 1.00-1.80 Neve

Table 4C presents the results for Teacher Support and Professional Learning. All five items received positive responses, with weighted means ranging from 4.40 to 4.72, indicating overall agreement that

teachers felt supported in their professional growth related to reading instruction. The access to professional learning opportunities related to teaching reading and encouraged to develop professionally in the area of reading instruction got the highest mean score of 4.50 while lowest mean was for receiving sufficient support to improve reading instruction practices and the Collaborative discussion with colleagues helped improve my reading instruction with the same mean of (4.40), The overall weighted mean of 4.48 suggests that teachers generally perceive strong professional support and learning opportunities in relation to reading instruction.

These findings align with research emphasizing the importance of teacher support, collaboration, and ongoing professional learning in improving instructional practices and student outcomes (Brown et al., 2023).

Tables 4A, 4B, and 4C show consistently high ratings across the three dimensions of instructional supervision: feedback and coaching, classroom environment and resources, and teacher support and professional learning. For Feedback and Coaching (Table 5A), all items received very high mean scores (4.72–4.85), with an overall weighted mean of 4.78, indicating that teachers strongly perceived feedback as clear, timely, and helpful for improving instruction. For Classroom Environment, Materials, and Assessment (Table 5B), the items also obtained high ratings (4.57–4.96), with an overall weighted mean of 4.69, suggesting that teachers viewed their classroom setup, resources, and assessment practices as supportive of reading instruction. For Teacher Support and Professional Learning (Table 5C), the weighted means ranged from 4.40 to 4.50, with an overall weighted mean of 4.46, indicating that teachers generally felt supported through professional learning opportunities, collaboration, and encouragement for professional growth.

Taken together, the results indicate that instructional supervision in terms of feedback and coaching, classroom environment and resources, and teacher support and professional learning is perceived very positively by teachers. The consistently high ratings suggest that these components collectively contribute to improved instructional practices and strengthen teachers' confidence and preparedness in teaching reading, which may in turn support better reading outcomes among pupils.

Level of the reading proficiency of Grades 1 to 3 pupils in terms of before the implementation of the instructional supervision and after the instructional supervision.

Table 5A. *Pre-test results of Reading Proficiency of Grades 1,2 and 3 learners (CRLA)*

Grade level	4(GR)		3(LR)		2(MR)		1(FR)		TOTAL		W \bar{X}	I
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
Grade 1	17	21.79	26	33.33	11	14.10	24	30.77	78	100	2.46	MR
Grade 2	40	51.95	9	11.69	11	14.29	17	22.10	77	100	2.94	LR
Grade 3	33	31.43	28	26.67	13	12.38	31	29.52	105	100	2.6	LR
Total/	90	34.62	63	24.23	35	34.46	72	27.69	260	100	2.66	LR
GeneralW \bar{X}												

Legend:3.26-4.00 Grade Ready(GR);2.51-3.25 Light Refresher(LR);1.76-2.50 Moderate Refresher(MR);1.00-1.75 Full Refresher (FR)

Table 5A shows the level of reading proficiency level of Grades 1 to 3 pupils based on the CRLA pre-test results. Reading proficiency is categorized into Grade Reader (GR), Light Refresher (LR), Moderate Refresher (MR) and Full Refresher (FR).

For Grade 1, the highest proportion of pupils belongs to the Light Refresher level (33.33%), followed by the Full Refresher (30.77%). The computed weighted mean of 2.46, interpreted as Moderate

Refresher (MR), indicates that most Grade 1 pupils are still developing basic reading skills and require guided reading instruction to improve comprehension and fluency.

In Grade 2, more than half of the pupils (51.95%) are classified as Grade Ready, suggesting a significant improvement in reading proficiency. The weighted mean of 2.94, interpreted as Light Refresher (LR), implies that while many pupils can already read independently, some still struggle with comprehension beyond the literal level.

For Grade 3, the results show a varied distribution across reading levels, with 31.43% identified as Grade Ready and 29.52% still at the Full Refresher level. The weighted mean of 2.60, interpreted as Light Refresher (LR), indicates that although reading skills have improved, a considerable number of pupils continue to experience reading difficulties.

Overall, the general weighted mean of 2.66, interpreted as Light Refresher (LR), reveals that the majority of Grades 1 to 3 pupils can comprehend texts at a basic literal level prior to intervention. However, the presence of many pupils in the Moderate and Full Refresher levels highlights the need for targeted reading programs to enhance early literacy skills.

Early reading Proficiency is a critical foundation for academic success, particularly in the primary grades. These findings suggest that early assessment and intervention are essential to improve reading outcomes among primary pupils.

However, the presence of many pupils in the Moderate and Full Refresher levels highlights the need for targeted reading programs to enhance early literacy skills. Early reading proficiency is a critical foundation for academic success, particularly in the primary grades, and these findings suggest that early assessment and intervention are essential to improve reading outcomes among primary pupils, consistent with research showing that targeted early reading strategies can effectively improve foundational reading skills (Silvia & Ishartiwi, 2025)

Table 5B. *Posttest results of Reading Proficiency of Grades 1,2 and 3 learners (CRLA)*

Grade level	4(GR)		3(LR)		2(MR)		1(FR)		TOTAL		W \bar{X}	I
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
Grade 1	46	58.97	24	30.77	3	3.85	5	6.41	78	100	3.42	GR
Grade 2	43	55.84	16	20.78	8	10.39	10	12.99	77	100	3.19	LR
Grade 3	57	52.29	16	15.24	22	20.95	10	9.52	105	100	3.14	LR
Total/ GeneralW \bar{X}	146	56.15	56	21.54	33	12.69	25	9.62	260	100	3.24	LR

Legend: 3.26-4.00 Grade Ready(GR); 2.51-3.25 Light Refresher(LR); 1.76-2.50 Moderate Refresher(MR); 1.00-1.75 Full Refresher (FR)

Table 5B presents the level of reading proficiency of Grades 1 to 3 pupils based on the CRLA post-test results. Reading proficiency levels are categorized as Grade Ready (GR), Light Refresher (LR), Moderate Refresher (MR), and Full Refresher (FR). For Grade 1, a substantial majority of pupils (58.97%) reach the Grade Ready level, while only 6.41% remain at the Light Refresher level. The weighted mean of 3.42, interpreted as Grade Ready (GR), indicates a marked improvement in reading proficiency compared to the pre-test results. In Grade 2, more than half of the pupils (55.84%) were classified as Grade Ready, with fewer pupils falling under the Moderate Refresher (10.39%) and Full Refresher (12.99%) levels. The computed weighted mean of 3.19, interpreted as Light Refresher (LR), suggests that most pupils demonstrated improved reading skills, particularly in comprehension and fluency. Similarly, Grade 3 pupils showed improvement, with 52.29% classified as Grade Ready and only 9.52% at the Light Refresher level. The weighted mean of 3.10, interpreted as Light Refresher (LR),

indicates that a majority of pupils were able to read with adequate understanding, though some still require additional support. Overall, the general weighted mean of 3.42, interpreted as Light Refresher (LR), reflects a significant improvement in the reading proficiency of Grades 1 to 3 pupils in the post test. The increased percentage of pupils at the Grade Ready level and the reduced number of Full Refresher suggest that the reading intervention was effective in enhancing pupils' reading abilities. These results are consistent with recent research demonstrating that early reading interventions and structured instructional support significantly improve foundational reading skills among primary learners (Martinez & Lopez, 2024). Therefore, the significant difference in Grades 1 to 3 pupils' reading proficiency before and after the instructional supervision intervention underscores the positive impact of targeted reading support.

The significant difference in Grade 1 to 3 pupils before and after the instructional supervision intervention in their reading proficiency;

Table 6. Pretest -posttest results of Grades 1,2 and 3 learners Reading Proficiency levels results (CRLA)

Paired Sample Statistics				
Grade1,2,3	Mean	N	Standard Deviation	Standard Error Mean
Pair 1;				
Pretest	2.44	78	1.16	0.13
Post-test	3.42	78	0.85	0.10
Pair 2;				
Pretest	2.11	77	1.28	0.14
Post-test	1.83	77	1.10	0.12
Pair 3;				
Pretest	2.32	105	1.17	0.11
Post-test	1.86	105	1.06	0.10

A sample t-test was performed to compare the scores between the Pre-test and Post-test of the Grade 1 pupils. There is a significant difference in scores between Pre-test (mean=2.44; SD 1.16) and Post test (mean=3.42; SD=0.88) with $t(78)=11.669$ and the p -value=0.000. Grade 2 a paired sample t-test was observed to compare the scores between the Pre-test and Post-test of the Grade 2 pupils. As presented in the table support this observation. Since the result of the test indicated that there is a significant difference in scores of reading proficiency of the grade 2 pupils Pre-test with the mean of 2.11 and standard deviation of 1.28, and Post-test with the mean 1.83 and standard Deviating 1.10. Grade 3 A sample t-test was given and utilized to compare the scores between the Pre-test and Post-test of the grade 3 pupils. The table revealed that there is a significant difference on the reading proficiency of the grade 3 pupils, Pre-test (Mean=2.32;SD=1.86) and Post-test (mean=1.86;SD=1.06) with the $t(105)=9.539$ and p -value=0.000. This suggests that the program was applied between.

Table 7. Pre-test -posttest results of Grades 1,2 and 3 learners Reading Proficiency levels results (CRLA)

Paired Difference								
Grade 1, 2, 3	Mean	SD	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		T	DF	P-Value
			Lower	Upper				
Pair 1:								
Pre-test	-	0.75	0.846	-	-8.8187	-	77	0.000
Posttest	0.987		1.15564			11.669		
Pair 2:								
Pre-test	0.282	0.45	0.051	0.17994	0.38417	5.500	76	0.0000
Posttest								
Pair 3:								
Pre-test	0.467	0.50	0.489	0.36966	0.56368	9.539	105	0.0000
Posttest								
0.05 level of significance							df=n-1	

The results revealed a statically significant difference between pre-test and post-test scores of the Grade 1 pupils, which ($p < 0.05$) indicating that the intervention had a significant effect on the respondent's performance. This suggests that the intervention program applied between the two scores of the Grade 1 pupils had an effect on the respondents. Grade 2, With the $t(77) = 5.500$ and the $p = 0.000$. This implies that the programs intervention did not support learning of the pupils as intended and may need replacement and revision and the result may not accurately reflect learning assessment tools must be restated and reviewed. For the Grade 3 The two scores of the Grade 3 pupils had an effect on the respondents.

CHAPTER 4

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presented the summary of findings, conclusion, and recommendations given the results of the study.

Summary of Findings

This study was conducted to determine the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) proficiency levels of key stage 1 learners: an instructional supervision-based study. The study sought to assess the pupils' reading performance in the pre-test and posttest to identify any significant changes in their reading proficiency levels. It investigated the effect of the instructional supervision program on the reading development of key stage 1 learners as measured by their reading assessment results. The study aimed to provide evidence on the effectiveness of the instructional supervision program in improving early reading skills and to serve as a basis for strengthening instructional practices in the district.

A one-group pretest–posttest research design was employed with key stage 1 learners from District 1, Cluster 2, San Carlos City as participants. Data were gathered using reading assessment tools administered before and after the implementation of the instructional supervision program. The results

yielded findings that demonstrated changes in pupils' reading proficiency levels, providing support for the role of instructional supervision in enhancing reading performance among early-grade learners.

The results of the study answered the following questions:

A survey was conducted to determine the levels of instructional supervision of Key stage 1 teachers before and after the implementation of instructional supervision in terms of feedback and coaching for reading instruction, classroom environment, materials and assessment for reading, and teacher support and professional learning. With generally high and very high levels of agreement, the findings indicate that teachers perceived instructional supervision as highly effective in enhancing their proficiency in reading instruction. Teachers expressed strong agreement that feedback and coaching were clear, timely, and actionable, and that supervisory support enabled meaningful professional dialogue and instructional improvement. Favorable perceptions were also evident regarding classroom environments, instructional materials, and assessment practices, indicating that teachers viewed these conditions as supportive of effective reading instruction. Furthermore, the results reveal positive perceptions of teacher support and professional learning, highlighting access to professional development opportunities, collaboration with colleagues, and encouragement for professional growth. Overall, the findings reflect affirming and supportive teacher perceptions of instructional supervision, demonstrating positive attitudes, increased confidence, and improved preparedness in teaching reading, and suggesting that instructional supervision is well-received and instrumental in strengthening reading instruction among Grades 1–3 teachers.

A Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) was conducted to determine the level of reading proficiency of key stage 1 learners before and after the implementation of the instructional supervision program. Prior to the intervention, the results showed that most pupils were classified under the Light Refresher and Moderate Refresher levels, indicating developing reading skills and the need for targeted reading support.

After the implementation of instructional supervision, the posttest results revealed a significant improvement in reading proficiency, with a notable increase in the number of learners classified as Grade Ready and a decrease in those under the Moderate and Full Refresher levels. Overall, the findings indicate that instructional supervision positively influenced pupils' reading proficiency and contributed to improved early literacy outcomes among Grades 1–3 pupils.

A paired sample t-test was conducted to determine whether there was a significant difference in the reading proficiency of Grades 1–3 pupils before and after the implementation of the instructional supervision program. The results revealed a statistically significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores across all grade levels at the 0.05 level of significance.

For Grade 1, the posttest mean score was significantly higher than the pretest mean, indicating a substantial improvement in reading proficiency after the intervention. Similarly, Grade 2 pupils showed a statistically significant difference between pretest and posttest scores, reflecting a change in reading performance following the intervention. In Grade 3, the results also showed a significant difference between pretest and posttest scores, suggesting that the instructional supervision program had a measurable effect on pupils' reading proficiency.

Overall, the findings indicate that the instructional supervision program resulted in significant changes in the reading proficiency of Grades 1–3 pupils, demonstrating its effectiveness in improving early reading skills.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

This study examined the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) proficiency levels of key stage 1 learners. It also explored the levels of instructional supervision experienced by teachers in terms of feedback and coaching for reading instruction, classroom environment, instructional materials and assessment, and teacher support and professional learning. The findings provide a comprehensive view of how instructional supervision influences both teaching practices and pupils' reading performance in the early grades.

The results revealed that Key stage 1 teachers perceived instructional supervision to be highly effective across all identified dimensions. Teachers reported receiving clear, timely, and actionable feedback, as well as meaningful coaching that supported instructional improvement in reading. Favorable perceptions were also evident regarding classroom environment, availability of instructional materials, assessment practices, and opportunities for professional learning. These findings indicate that instructional supervision fostered a supportive and collaborative professional environment that enhanced teachers' confidence and preparedness in teaching reading.

In terms of learners' reading proficiency, the pretest results of the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy (CRLA) eliminate showed that many key stage 1 learners were initially classified under the Light Refresher and Moderate Refresher levels, reflecting developing reading skills and the need for targeted instructional support. After the implementation of instructional supervision, the posttest results demonstrated a noticeable improvement in reading proficiency, with an increased number of pupils classified as Grade Ready and a decrease in those requiring intensive reading intervention. This shift suggests that improved instructional practices contributed positively to pupils' reading development.

Furthermore, the paired sample t-test results confirmed that the differences between the pretest and posttest scores of Comprehensive Rapid Literacy (CRLA) learners' were statistically significant. These findings indicate that the instructional supervision program had a measurable and positive effect on learners reading proficiency. Overall, the study concludes that effective instructional supervision strengthens teaching practices and significantly improves early reading outcomes, emphasizing its importance in promoting literacy development among primary-grade learners.

Recommendation

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, several key recommendations are proposed to further enhance reading proficiency and instructional practices among Key Stage 1 learners and teachers:

School Administrators. The school administrators are encouraged to strengthen and sustain structured instructional supervision focused on early literacy. They should use Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) results to guide classroom observations, provide timely and constructive feedback, and implement targeted reading interventions. Aligning supervision practices with the standards of the Department of Education will further ensure consistency and help improve teachers' instructional practices and learners' reading proficiency.

Students. Students are encouraged to actively participate in reading activities and take responsibility for improving their literacy skills. They should use feedback from teachers and Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) results to recognize their strengths and areas for improvement, practice reading regularly both in school and at home, and seek support whenever needed. By developing consistent reading habits and a positive attitude toward learning, students can gradually enhance their reading proficiency and overall academic performance.

Teachers. Teachers are encouraged to continuously enhance their reading instruction through reflective practice and active engagement in instructional supervision. They should use Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) results to guide differentiated instruction, provide targeted support to struggling readers, and strengthen key literacy skills such as phonemic awareness, vocabulary, fluency, and comprehension. By remaining open to feedback, collaborating with school heads, and aligning their

strategies with the standards of the Department of Education, teachers can improve instructional effectiveness and help raise learners' reading proficiency.

Curriculum Planners and Policy Makers. These personnel should strengthen early literacy frameworks by integrating structured instructional supervision into reading programs. They should use Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) data to refine curriculum guides, develop responsive teacher training modules, and ensure that reading interventions are aligned with the standards of the Department of Education. By grounding policies and curriculum decisions in empirical evidence, they can promote more effective literacy instruction and improve reading outcomes among Key Stage 1 learners.

Future Researchers. It is suggested that future researchers replicate the study in different districts or educational settings to validate and expand the results. They may also explore additional variables such as parental involvement, socioeconomic factors, or the use of digital literacy tools that may influence reading proficiency. Conducting longitudinal or comparative studies could further provide deeper insights into the long-term impact of instructional supervision on learners' literacy development.

CRLA Reading Supervision Program: Enhancing Early Literacy Skills

Program

Objectives:

The program objectives are (1) to improve Grades 1–3 pupils' CRLA-aligned reading proficiency through structured instructional supervision, (2) to enhance teachers' capacity in reading instruction through targeted coaching, feedback, and professional learning, (3) to strengthen classroom reading environments and access to appropriate reading materials, (4) to monitor and track pupils' reading progress using evidence-based assessments, and (5) to foster a positive and supportive learning culture conducive to literacy development.

Teachers' Training and Development:

(1) Conduct workshops and training sessions to familiarize teachers with CRLA reading standards and instructional strategies.(2) Provide guidance on effective reading assessment interpretation and data-driven instructional planning.(3) Implement a coaching phase where supervisors model CRLA-aligned reading lessons and provide actionable feedback.(4) Phase 2: Train teachers on differentiated instruction techniques to support diverse reading levels in Grades 1–3 (Light, Moderate, and Full Refresher levels).

Instructional Supervision and Feedback:

(1) Conduct regular classroom observations focusing on reading instruction, including vocabulary, comprehension, and fluency.(2) Provide timely and constructive feedback that is clear, actionable, and aligned with CRLA standards.(3) Establish a mentorship system where experienced teachers guide peers in implementing effective reading practices.(4) Phase 3: Implement peer reflection sessions for teachers to share best practices and collaboratively address reading challenges.

Classroom Environment and Learning Materials:

(1) Review and enhance classroom environments to ensure they are conducive to reading (e.g., reading corners, visual aids, leveled libraries).(2) Provide CRLA-aligned instructional resources, including leveled texts, comprehension worksheets, and interactive reading tools.(3) Encourage teachers to integrate varied reading materials to cater to pupils' developmental needs and reading levels.(4) Phase 4: Audit classroom resources to ensure alignment with CRLA standards and effective literacy instruction.

Student Support and Engagement:

(1) Implement targeted reading interventions for pupils at Light and Moderate Refresher levels.(2) Organize guided reading sessions, reading clubs, and literacy games to engage pupils in active learning.(3) Encourage a positive learning culture where pupils feel motivated and supported in developing reading skills.(4) Phase 5: Monitor pupils' reading progress regularly and adjust interventions based on assessment results.

Stakeholder Communication and Engagement:

(1) Maintain open communication with parents, teachers, and school administrators regarding pupils' reading progress and program activities.(2) Provide workshops and materials for parents to support reading at home.(3) Collect feedback from stakeholders to continuously improve reading instruction and supervision practices.

Articulation of the Program:

(1) Phase 6: Map reading instruction horizontally (across classrooms) and vertically (across grade levels) to ensure continuity and progression of CRLA skills.(2) Align lesson plans and assessment tools with CRLA benchmarks for early literacy.(3) Ensure teachers have a clear roadmap for delivering sequential and scaffolded reading instruction.

Program Evaluation:

(1) Assess the impact of the CRLA Reading Supervision Program on pupils' reading proficiency and teacher practices.(2) Conduct pre- and post-reading assessments to measure improvements in vocabulary, comprehension, fluency, and overall reading levels.(3) Solicit feedback from teachers, pupils, and parents to evaluate program effectiveness and areas for enhancement.

Program Sustainability:

(1) Establish ongoing professional development cycles for teachers to maintain reading instruction competency.(2) Conduct periodic classroom audits to ensure adherence to CRLA-aligned instructional practices.(3) Maintain a repository of effective reading materials and teaching resources.(4) Implement regular program review sessions to adapt interventions to changing student needs.(5) Integrate the program into the institutional culture to ensure long-term commitment and engagement.(6) Foster a culture of recognition and celebration to sustain motivation among teachers and pupils.

Table 1. *CRLA Reading Supervision Program: Enhancing Early Literacy Skills*

Timeline	Phase	Activities	Persons In-Charge	Budget and Sourcing	Monitoring and Evaluation	Sustainability	Success Indicators
Months 1-3	Preparation (Phase 1)	- Conduct teacher training sessions on CRLA reading standards and instructional strategies.- Provide guidance on reading assessment interpretation and data-driven instructional planning.	Academic Coordinator / Training Coordinator	- Allocate funds for training materials, resources, and venue (if offsite).	- Assess teacher participation and engagement in training sessions.- Evaluate effectiveness of training through pre/post knowledge checks.	- Establish a system for continuous teacher development.- Maintain a repository of CRLA-aligned teaching resources.	-At least 90% of Key Stage 1 teachers complete the CRLA training. -Teachers demonstrate at least 20% improvement in post-training knowledge assessment scores. -Submission of at least one

							<p>CRLA-aligned lesson plan per teacher.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Functional and accessible repository of CRLA instructional materials established.
Months 4-6	Instructional Supervision & Coaching (Phase 2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implement coaching phase where supervisors model CRLA-aligned reading lessons.- Provide actionable feedback.- Train teachers on differentiated instruction techniques for Light, Moderate, and Full Refresher levels. 	<p>Training Coordinator / Academic Coordinator / Supervisors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Budget for coaching sessions, demonstration lessons, and teaching aids. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitor integration of new instructional strategies in classroom practice.- Collect feedback from teachers on coaching effectiveness. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide ongoing support and resources for teachers.- Encourage mentorship between experienced and novice teachers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At least 85-90% of observed teachers demonstrate integration of CRLA-aligned strategies during classroom observations. - Improvement in classroom observation ratings compared to baseline supervision data. - Positive teacher feedback (e.g., 4.0 or higher mean rating) on coaching effectiveness. - Increase in the number of pupils moving from Full/Moderate Refresher to higher proficiency levels in interim assessments.
Months 7-9	Classroom Environment & Learning Materials (Phase 3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Review and enhance classroom reading environments (reading corners, visual aids, leveled libraries).- Provide CRLA-aligned resources: leveled texts, comprehension worksheets, 	<p>Academic Coordinator / Resource Committee</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Allocate budget for classroom materials, leveled books, and interactive tools. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evaluate classroom setups and resource utilization.- Gather teacher feedback on resource effectiveness. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maintain and update classroom reading materials.- Promote continuous improvement of literacy instructional resources. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 100% of Key Stage 1 classrooms establish functional reading corners with CRLA-aligned materials. - At least 80-90% of

		interactive reading tools.- Audit classroom resources for alignment with CRLA standards.					audited materials meet CRLA standards. Increased pupil engagement during reading activities based on classroom observation reports. - Observable improvement in interim CRLA reading proficiency results after resource enhancement.
Months 10-12	Student Support & Articulation (Phase 4)	- Implement targeted reading interventions for pupils at Light and Moderate levels.- Organize guided reading sessions, reading clubs, and literacy games.- Map reading instruction horizontally and vertically for continuity of CRLA skills.- Align lesson plans and assessment tools with CRLA benchmarks.	Academic Coordinator / Supervisors / Teachers	- Budget for intervention materials, guided reading resources, and assessment tools.	- Monitor pupil progress using evidence-based assessments.- Evaluate alignment of lesson plans and assessments with CRLA benchmarks.	- Adjust interventions based on assessment results.- Ensure teachers have a clear roadmap for sequential and scaffolded reading instruction.- Foster a positive learning culture among pupils.	-At least 80% of pupils in Light and Moderate Refresher levels show measurable improvement in CRLA post-assessments. - All lesson plans and assessments demonstrate alignment with CRLA standards. -Increased pupil participation and engagement in guided reading sessions and literacy activities. -Positive teacher feedback on the effectiveness and continuity of reading interventions.
Ongoing	Monitoring, Evaluation & Sustainability (Phase 5)	- Conduct pre- and post-reading assessments.- Solicit feedback	Evaluation Team / Academic Coordinator	- Budget for assessment tools, evaluation	- Analyze pupil reading proficiency improvements.-	- Maintain ongoing professional development	Continuous improvement in pupil CRLA

		from teachers, pupils, and parents.- Regular classroom audits to ensure adherence to CRLA-aligned practices.- Periodic program review sessions.	/ School Principal	activities, and audit logistics.	Assess impact on teacher practices and classroom literacy culture.- Collect stakeholder feedback.	cycles.- Integrate program into institutional culture.- Foster a culture of recognition and celebration for teachers and pupils.- Update and sustain teaching resources and interventions.	reading proficiency over successive assessments. At least 90% of teachers consistently implement CRLA-aligned instructional strategies. Positive stakeholder feedback (teachers, pupils, parents) with mean satisfaction rating ≥ 4.0 . Regularly updated repository of teaching resources maintained and utilized by teachers. Evidence of program integration into school culture, such as literacy events, reading campaigns, or recognition programs.
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